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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Two-Way Confidential VMs (2cVM): Collaborative Confidential Computing for Mutually Distrustful Parties

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ABSTRACT Collaborative computation across organizations is often constrained by the need to process sensitive data and proprietary code without exposing them to untrusted infrastructure or participants. Cryptographic approaches such as fully homomorphic encryption and secure multi-party computation provide strong confidentiality but remain impractical for general workloads due to their extreme computational cost. We present the *Two-Way Confidential Virtual Machine (2cVM)*, a two-layer architecture that pairs a hardware trusted execution environment with an intra-workload isolation layer. Unlike regular Confidential Virtual Machines, 2cVM enforces mutual isolation between co-resident workloads, ensuring that participants retain control over their data and code. All computation in 2cVM is governed by a *Commitment Manifest* that enumerates participants, component composition, permitted data channels, and authorized outputs; the manifest is locked to the VM and incorporated into attestation evidence, making the policy immutable and independently verifiable throughout the VM's lifetime. A proof-of-concept realization combines AMD SEV-SNP for hardware protection with the WebAssembly Component Model for fine-grained sandboxing of participant code. Evaluation on commodity hardware across four benchmark classes shows that the two isolation layers do not accumulate linearly: once a workload executes inside the WebAssembly sandbox, the marginal cost of enabling hardware memory protection is small. Overhead is workload-dependent, governed primarily by memory access pattern, ranging from negligible for sequential workloads to approximately $2\times$ for irregular, pointer-chasing access patterns. These results indicate that 2cVM provides a practical and verifiable foundation for privacy-preserving collaborative computation.

INDEX TERMS Confidential computing, trusted execution environments, WebAssembly component model, zero-trust.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many useful computations require data held by different organizations. Hospitals need to combine patient data to build reliable diagnostic models, but the data is sensitive and legally protected. Manufacturers need to combine production data with their suppliers to detect faults, but doing so exposes trade secrets. Defense systems require shared operational data to

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improve performance, yet that data is classified and often heavily siloed. In each case, collaboration would yield better results, but sharing the data itself carries unacceptable risk.

One of the central obstacles in inter-organizational computation is the loss of control that occurs once data leaves the environment of its owner [25]. Initiatives such as European data spaces formalize data sharing agreements and governance models, but they remain largely policy- and contract-based; verifying and auditing compliance is difficult and costly. Regulatory requirements such as the GDPR add

further constraints on cross-organizational data processing that any deployed system must eventually address. This challenge underscores the need for a zero-trust approach, where no infrastructure or participant is implicitly trusted, and all interactions are governed by verifiable policies.

Cryptographic approaches such as Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) and secure multi-party computation (MPC) offer strong confidentiality guarantees but remain several orders of magnitude slower than native execution. Even with extensive algorithmic and hardware acceleration, recent studies show that their performance is still far from practical [19], [41]. Consequently, these schemes are limited to specialized and latency-insensitive workloads.

This article introduces the *Two-Way Confidential Virtual Machine* (2cVM), a protected execution environment for collaborative computation among mutually distrusting parties. Each participant contributes code and data as an isolated component. Interaction between components is restricted to a definition that all parties agree to in advance. These permitted interactions are recorded in a novel *Commitment Manifest*, a document, cryptographically bound to the VM's attested state, describing the future behavior of the confidential computing environment that cannot be altered at runtime, a feature that conventional confidential computing does not offer.

The 2cVM builds on hardware-backed confidential computing but extends its security model. A standard Confidential Virtual Machine (CVM) hides the workload from the host, but it assumes that everything inside the VM is mutually trusted. The 2cVM removes that assumption and enforces confidentiality between co-resident workloads. It provides strong, verifiable isolation at the component boundary and ensures that data only moves along authorized paths.

This turns data-use policy into a technical property of the execution environment. Each party can verify the computational structure before contributing data, and the system offers future guarantees that no other component can access or infer that data outside the declared channels. The result is collaborative computation in which control is retained, misuse is technically prevented, and trust between participants is no longer a prerequisite, making it suitable as a technical enforcement layer of data-sharing agreements.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows. Section II provides the technical background on which our design builds. Section V describes the security model for the 2cVM architecture. Section III examines related work both in academia and industry. The following sections then detail our main **Contributions**:

- Section IV: the **Two-Way Confidential Virtual (2cVM) architecture**,¹ which extends existing confidential computing models through a dual-layer isolation design that protects against both host infiltration and guest exfiltration. It introduces the novel abstract concept of the *Commitment Manifest* as a verifiable

link between attested hardware and component-level policy enforcement throughout the VM's lifecycle, enabling mutual assurance between data owners and code providers.

- Section VI: an open-source [24] **proof-of-concept implementation** demonstrating the practical feasibility of 2cVM on commodity SEV-SNP hardware and its integration with the WebAssembly Component Model.
- Section VII: a **quantitative validation of 2cVM's practicality** across varied categories of benchmarks, demonstrating generalizability across workloads with distinct computational profiles.

Finally, Section VIII discusses the limitations of the 2cVM implementation and its underlying technologies, Section IX provides a conclusion, and Section X outlines future research directions.

II. BACKGROUND

A. CONFIDENTIAL VIRTUAL MACHINES

Confidential computing (CC) is a technology that protects data in use by applying hardware-enforced encryption and integrity protections to system memory. Over the past two decades, it has evolved rapidly. Feng et al. [15] identify three distinct stages, the most recent beginning around 2019 with the shift from specialized, process-level enclave systems such as Intel SGX [4] to general-purpose confidential virtual machines (CVM) such as AMD SEV-SNP [1] in 2020 and Intel TDX [23] in 2021. This transition expanded the protection boundary from isolated application processes to entire virtual machines, enabling full operating systems and unmodified applications to execute securely on untrusted hosts.

Remote attestation (RA) is a core mechanism in confidential computing. It allows a remote party to verify the integrity and configuration of a confidential VM before provisioning secrets or initiating execution. The hardware produces a signed attestation report containing cryptographic measurements of components that form the basis of trust, collectively referred to as the trusted computing base (TCB).

Four attestation levels (AL1 to AL4) can be distinguished for confidential VMs [40]. AL1 attests the physical platform and confidential hardware, that is, the processor package and on-chip security engine, and binds an attestation key to a genuine device in a known configuration. AL2 covers the platform firmware that implements memory protection and bootstraps the guest, including microcode updates, BIOS or UEFI, and the confidential runtime firmware. AL3 attests the guest operating system kernel (e.g., a Linux kernel image) that defines the protection domain inside the CVM. AL4 extends attestation to the rest of the software stack, including system services, middleware, language runtimes, and application workloads.

In practical deployments, these attestation levels are instantiated as a chain of measurements and verifications that propagates trust from the physical platform (AL1) through firmware (AL2) to the guest and, ideally, its workloads

¹European Patent Application No. EP25187609.0 (pending, unpublished).

(AL3–AL4). In their most basic form, however, deployed CVM attestations focus on the lower levels, primarily AL1 and AL2, and provide assurance only about the initial launch state of the system. This is limiting for full virtual machines, which evolve as kernels, drivers, and user-space components are loaded at runtime.

Recent developments incorporate virtual Trusted Platform Modules (vTPMs) [34], [36] and measured boot techniques that retain integrity evidence across attestation levels. By securely storing and extending measurements through the startup sequence, these mechanisms enable verification of a broader portion of the software stack, including the guest kernel, and selected user-space components up to AL4.

A verifier that does not want to blindly trust the cloud provider must be able to reconstruct this chain and check each link independently, which in turn requires that the components responsible for measurement and evidence generation, such as firmware, bootloaders, agents, and verification services, use open, well-specified formats and, preferably, open-source implementations. In practice, cloud providers do not always expose attestation evidence for the entire software stack, and tenants often receive guarantees about platform and launch state but little or no visibility into the code that actually executes inside the VM [40]. Recent policy work, including recommendations from national cybersecurity agencies, argues that open-source CVM firmware and standard attestation protocols are prerequisites for such independently verifiable, zero-trust use of confidential computing. [16]

B. WEBASSEMBLY

WebAssembly (Wasm) is a portable binary instruction format that compiles high-level languages to a well-defined abstract machine, enabling execution across heterogeneous hardware and operating environments. Originally designed as a high-performance execution environment for browsers, its sandbox-by-default model and competitive performance have facilitated adoption in other domains such as serverless computing [26] and cloud-edge systems [33].

To enable execution outside the browser, the **WebAssembly System Interface (WASI)** [50] was introduced. WASI defines a standardized, capability-based set of host APIs that provide controlled access to system resources such as filesystem interfaces, clocks and randomness sources. Proposals such as *wasi-sockets* and *wasi-http* extend this model to networking and higher-level services, enabling progressively richer application support while maintaining strict isolation boundaries. Because capabilities must be explicitly granted, modules cannot access resources they were not provided, preserving WebAssembly's sandboxed design even when performing external I/O.

To enhance modularity and interoperability among Wasm applications, the **WebAssembly Component Model** [49] is being developed within the WebAssembly standards community. The component model introduces a structured approach

to composing applications from multiple Wasm components, describing imports and exports in the WebAssembly Interface Types (WIT) language and enabling interoperability across languages without exposing internal memory layouts. This abstraction extends portability beyond operating systems and architectures to language boundaries: for example, a Go component can invoke a Rust component through a typed interface without shared memory. Components interact only through declared functions and types, which enforces isolation and provides clear definitions of inter-component communications.

III. RELATED WORK

The following sections analyze the body of existing work, both in research and industry, and contrast it to 2cVM.

A. ACADEMIC PROJECTS

1) CRYPTOGRAPHIC SECURE COMPUTATION

These approaches rely on mathematical hardness to protect data in-use. Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), for example allows a server to process encrypted data. They offer strong, formally provable confidentiality guarantees but have the downside that their overhead is several orders of magnitude larger than native execution. Recent studies show that FHE is still far from practical for any workloads that take longer than a few milliseconds to execute in plaintext, even with hardware acceleration [19], [28], [41], [53]. Moreover, porting an existing algorithm to FHE often requires deep expertise in FHE and sometimes even new cryptographic primitives [45]. Furthermore, standard FHE does not hide the algorithm used to process the data and does not support multiple mutually untrusting clients [17]. Circuit-private FHE [10] hides the algorithm from the clients, but not from the server. Although extensions such as multi-key FHE [3] aim to address some of these issues, they often increase the overhead even more.

2) AccTEE

AccTEE [18] proposes a two-way sandbox for mutually distrustful workload and infrastructure providers. It combines an SGX enclave with a WebAssembly runtime and instruction-level accounting to produce an attested resource-usage log. Its trust boundary is primarily vertical: SGX protects the workload's code and data from the host, while the WASM sandbox and instrumentation protect the host and ensure an accurate representation of cloud resource usage. By contrast, 2cVM targets horizontal distrust between multiple code and data providers that share a confidential VM. Rather than metering resources for a single tenant, 2cVM uses its WebAssembly isolation layer to protect guests from one another in a collaborative computing environment.

3) WAVEN

WAVEN [47] targets a similar use-case to 2cVM: collaborative confidential computing with multiple distrustful

parties. However, where 2cVM provides a full high-level architecture, WAVEN focuses on the technical challenge of sharing memory pages between WebAssembly modules. It replaces Wasm's linear memory with a software-managed virtual memory layer so that each module gets its own logical address space and the platform can share memory pages between modules with per-module read or read-write access. The entire runtime runs inside an SGX enclave, which hides tenant code and data from the host and lets data providers and consumers attest that the expected platform binary is executing. Its *policy* is essentially which modules may map which shared pages with which permissions, inside a single fixed runtime. It does not provide an explicit, attested manifest that names participants, describes which components they contribute, or constrains which data may flow to which party. In contrast, 2cVM provides a higher-level *Commitment Manifest* that is sealed into the attested state of the CVM and governs component composition and data channels; WAVEN's memory virtualization could be used to enforce such decisions inside the 2cVM runtime, but it does not address manifest-level governance by itself.

4) RYOAN

Ryoan [22] provides a distributed sandbox for untrusted data-processing services. Its design is oriented towards a request-driven pipeline over a single user's input, defined as a directed acyclic graph (DAG) of processing services. A modified Native Client (NaCl) [20] sandbox inside SGX enclaves runs each module, while Ryoan's runtime enforces that data flows only along the DAG edges, restricts external I/O, and resets every sandbox after each request to limit stateful leakage beyond the pipeline. This model explicitly targets single-user data-processing pipelines and does not support long-lived joint computation across data from multiple mutually distrustful parties, nor does it expose a separate, attested policy abstraction beyond the DAG structure itself. 2cVM expands beyond this per-request pipeline model: the *Commitment Manifest* describes long-lived compositions of multiple datasets and code components within a confidential VM and attaches explicit permissions specifying which participants may access which inputs and outputs, with the manifest itself sealed into the VM's attested state.

B. INDUSTRY PROJECTS

1) AZURE CONFIDENTIAL CLEAN ROOMS

Azure Confidential Clean Rooms [30] aim to enable collaborative processing of sensitive data within confidential applications. However, their design remains more constrained and more dependent on external trust anchors than the 2cVM. The *Clean Room Specification* defines which data sources and sinks are available, which applications may run, and which external endpoints are exposed for governance and monitoring. It also includes sandboxing and configuration metadata that roughly correspond to the scope of the 2cVM *Commitment Manifest*.

Despite this resemblance, the *Clean Room Specification* diverges in several important ways. It defines isolation policies rather than composition policies. Once data enters the clean room, all components appear to have mutual visibility, with no explicit mediation or selective sharing between them. Isolation is enforced only at the perimeter: policies restrict external communication but do not govern internal data flow or component interaction. In contrast, the 2cVM *Commitment Manifest* captures the complete composition of components and their permitted interconnections, which allows selective and attestable enforcement of data and code boundaries inside the 2cVM.

The trust model further limits the *Clean Room Specification*'s guarantees. The specification is stored externally in a *Clean Room Governance Service* that relies on a distributed ledger and can be modified through consensus or administrative voting. Because of this mutability, it provides no definite guarantee about future behavior. Governance decisions, such as admitting a new application, depend on external consent authorities rather than being cryptographically bound to the execution environment. The 2cVM approach inverts this dependency by sealing the *Commitment Manifest* inside the confidential environment and including it in the attested state, which gives participants cryptographic assurance that the governing policy cannot change.

Azure's implementation also faces several practical constraints. Component communication is limited to HTTP, and authorization policies are expressed only as OPA rules applied to HTTP messages. Data sharing occurs through files instead of memory or structured data exchange, which limits efficiency for multi-party workloads. Component isolation depends on containers, a weaker boundary than 2cVM's isolation mechanisms, and identity management depends on third-party external services that must be trusted.

2) COCOS.AI

Cocos AI [44] provides a confidential computing platform designed for privacy-preserving machine learning workloads. Its architecture combines confidential virtual machines with in-enclave agents and encrypted communication channels across participants. A computation manifest specifies which datasets and algorithms are involved in a collaborative run, along with participant identities, and this manifest can be reflected in attestation.

Cocos is designed primarily for AI pipelines rather than broader multi-party collaboration across heterogeneous code. While it supports general-purpose workloads through containerization, this flexibility does not provide inherent isolation between workloads within the enclave, nor does it prevent workloads from colluding or attempting data exfiltration when they share the same trust domain. The computation manifest describes which components and datasets are present, but it does not define how these components compose, how data moves between them, or which internal interactions are allowed or prohibited. It therefore governs

deployment rather than internal data-flow or component boundaries.

By contrast, 2cVM is designed for general collaborative computing where parties may not trust one another. The *Commitment Manifest* in 2cVM specifies the component composition and the permitted data channels inside the enclave, and this specification is sealed into the attested state. This provides explicit, verifiable guarantees about how workloads may interact and how data may be accessed or released during and after execution.

3) ENARX

Enarx [13] is an open-source framework designed for running unmodified applications in trusted execution environments, combining a WebAssembly runtime with attestation for Intel SGX and AMD SEV. The intent was to provide a unified approach so developers could build applications without handling hardware-specific enclave details while users benefited from stronger guarantees around data confidentiality and code integrity. To minimize the trusted computing base, Enarx runs workloads on a custom microkernel supporting a Wasm runtime.

That design choice imposed tradeoffs. The reliance on a bespoke kernel and a tightly coupled Wasmtime fork makes it difficult to adopt modern WebAssembly features such as the component model and complicates integration with multiple mutually distrustful workloads supported by 2cVM. Enarx assumes a single workload and lacks mechanisms to govern data flow or enforce mutual isolation between cooperating parties. It also depends on centralized registry and attestation services for workload distribution and trust establishment, which is a problematic model in zero-trust settings where participants avoid disclosing code or metadata to a third party.

The project has seen limited maintenance since its parent company Profian, shut down in 2023 [5], leaving its companion services offline and documentation outdated. As a result, Enarx is impractical to deploy today.

IV. ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

This section outlines the architecture of the Two-Way Confidential VM. It first introduces the design goals, then provides an overview of the components that make up the 2cVM.

A. DESIGN GOALS

The *Two-Way Confidential Virtual Machine* architecture was designed with the following goals in mind:

- 1) Extend the default security model of Confidential VMs with **protections against exfiltration** by malicious code, provided by one of the parties, running inside the CVM.
- 2) Make this environment as **multi-purpose and generic** as possible, allowing for an arbitrary number of participants to collaboratively compute using an arbitrary number of computational components, operating on an arbitrary number of data sets.

- 3) Enable **verifiable governance** in a way that is compatible, but not limited to, existing solutions such as data spaces.

B. CONCEPTUAL COMPONENTS

A schematic overview of the key conceptual components that make up the 2cVM is presented in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. Overview of the Two-Way Confidential Virtual Machine architecture. Multiple independent trust domains contribute code and data to a shared execution environment on an untrusted host. The Attestation Agent enforces the negotiated Commitment Manifest, which governs data channels and defines the isolation and composition of workloads.

The **Commitment Manifest** is the core directive of the 2cVM and defines all its operations. It is an abstract representation of the future behavior of the confidential computing environment. This makes it possible for the platform to not only attest its current state, but also its future behavior, even after its state and executable code changed. On a practical level, the manifest is a document which translates human-defined trust and security parameters into a machine-readable contract. It contains at least: a description of the participants, including an identifier used for authentication; a description of the code components, their composition, and capability-based I/O permissions; and a description of the data shared, as well as policies and ownership definitions related to this data. It is negotiated between participating parties prior to deployment.

The **Commitment Manifest Lock** is a conceptual state in which the platform code is bound to the commitment manifest in a way such that it can only perform the behavior described by the commitment manifest. As part of this state, the *Commitment Manifest* is bound to the platform attestation, extending the TCB’s cryptographic coverage to encompass the defined trust and security parameters at AL4. Any participant requesting attestation evidence after the commitment manifest lock goes into effect, will receive a cryptographically signed guarantee of both the current state and the future behavior of the platform.

The **Attestation Agent** serves as the central control point for the 2cVM. It is a trusted entity in the 2cVM architecture, included in the attestation chain at AL4. Its position in the trust chain requires it to be open-source or otherwise audited by all involved parties so it can function as a guarantor of future behavior. The agent is responsible for enacting the Commitment Manifest Lock by strictly enforcing policies defined in the *Commitment Manifest* such as admitting and releasing code and data, and by configuring the platform components to deny any unauthorized interference or modifications. The *Attestation Agent* provides verifiable attested evidence that both the 2cVM and the active *Commitment Manifest* are in the expected trust state, allowing each party to independently confirm that the environment enforces the negotiated security constraints.

The **Runtime** is a critical component to ensure all policies of the Commitment Manifest are fully enforced during execution of the workloads. This runtime is directed by the Attestation Agent to follow the explicitly authorized capabilities from the Commitment Manifest. This runtime layer is not tied to a particular technology, as long as it can provide fine-grained isolation and enforce capability-bound execution. For example, using the WebAssembly Component Model, the agent can assign narrowly scoped permissions that prevent unauthorized data movement or access, creating a strict sandbox around potentially untrusted code. Important to consider is that the enforcement of the Commitment Manifest depends on the runtime's ability to isolate individual workloads. For example, the runtime is responsible for protecting against side channel attacks. More hardened solutions such as hardware-based virtualization should be considered for situations with higher security requirements.

The **untrusted host** is a machine capable of running confidential workloads such as enclaves or confidential VMs. It provides 2cVM's second isolation layer, protecting against host infiltration. The host must be capable of attesting the state of this confidential runtime to a remote party up to and including AL2. Anything that can not be attested, such as the host kernel and hypervisor, is considered untrusted. This machine can be located either in the public cloud or the private cloud of one of the participants. A 2cVM instance is deployed to a confidential environment on this untrusted host. This instance contains all required components such as the guest kernel, guest OS, the runtime and the *Attestation Agent*. This instance must support attestation up to and including AL4, which includes the *Commitment Manifest*.

The **Connector** is a software component running within the trust boundary of each participating organization. Its job is to facilitate interactions with the 2cVM through the *Attestation Agent*. An authorized party's connector will lock an agreed-upon *Commitment Manifest* to the 2cVM. Each connector then interacts with the agent to verify the 2cVM and *Commitment Manifest* attestation before sending their respective data or code into the 2cVM. Each party trusts their

own connector. This connector can optionally be compatible with data spaces to provide an integration into its governance framework.

V. SECURITY MODEL

Having described the 2cVM architecture, this section outlines the security model under which the system is analyzed.

We consider a system consisting of an untrusted host platform H (including hypervisor), a secure confidential computing platform P , and a confidential virtual machine G instantiated from image I . The platform P provides memory confidentiality, memory integrity, and remote attestation capabilities. Upon launch, G undergoes a measured boot sequence (AL1–AL4), producing a measurement μ that reflects the hardware-rooted launch state, including the guest kernel and user-space runtime.

The image I contains an attestation agent A and a sandboxed in-guest runtime W , both covered by μ . The runtime W executes components $C_1 \dots C_n$ over datasets $D_1 \dots D_n$, all contributed by parties $X_1 \dots X_n$. A commitment manifest σ specifies the permitted component composition and allowed syntactic data access policies between components and with external I/O.

To provision data D_n or code C_n , each party X_n operates a remote connector V_n within its own trusted environment. During attestation, A generates an ephemeral key pair (pk_G, sk_G) inside G . It requests a report

$$\rho = \text{Attest}_P(\mu, H(pk_G), n),$$

where n is a nonce supplied by V_n to ensure freshness. The report ρ binds the measured launch state μ to the public key pk_G . The agent then signs the commitment manifest σ using sk_G and provides $(\rho, pk_G, \text{Sig}_{sk_G}(\sigma))$ to each connector V_n . Each V_n verifies the attestation report, checks freshness, verifies the signature over σ , and provisions D_n only if all checks succeed.

A. ADVERSARY MODEL

We consider a probabilistic polynomial-time adversary that fully controls the host platform H , including the hypervisor, operating system, and network. The adversary may attempt to launch G with a modified configuration or boot chain, replay, delay, inject, or suppress network messages, provide malicious components or datasets, and collude across multiple parties. The adversary may arbitrarily schedule, pause, or terminate G .

B. ASSUMPTIONS

We assume that P correctly enforces memory confidentiality and integrity of G with respect to H and produces unforgeable attestation reports. The measured launch sequence (AL1–AL4) correctly binds the guest kernel, A , and W into the measurement μ . Cryptographic primitives used for attestation and hashing are assumed secure.

As 2cVM's security posture is inherently linked to the confidential platform P . Security against physical attacks and

side-channel leakage is thus inherited and delegated to said underlying platform P . The impact of this is discussed in Section VIII-C.

We further assume that W correctly enforces memory isolation between components and restricts inter-component communication and access to external resources to channels declared in σ . This enforcement is syntactic: W constrains which channels exist and which capabilities are granted, but does not inspect or constrain the semantic content of information conveyed through authorized channels.

Denial-of-service attacks are considered out-of-scope. While these attacks can impact the availability of the agent and the runtime, they do not impact the security goals described below.

C. SECURITY GOALS

The following security goals are described here and evaluated in Section VII-G.

- 1) **Host Isolation.** For any adversary controlling H , the confidentiality and integrity of C_n and D_n within G are preserved with respect to H . In particular, H cannot learn plaintext contents except via outputs explicitly permitted by σ , nor modify the in-memory state of G , including A and W , without detection by P .
- 2) **Measured Launch Integrity.** Any deviation from the expected AL1–AL4 launch state, including modifications to A or W , results in a different measurement μ and therefore an attestation report that fails verification by honest connectors.
- 3) **Component Isolation and Policy Enforcement.** Assuming correct enforcement by W , data sharing between components and access to external resources occur only through channels declared in σ . If σ does not authorize access from C_i to C_j , then C_j has no program-visible channel through which to observe C_i 's state or inputs. Similarly, observable outputs from any component are restricted to channels explicitly authorized in σ and cannot be introduced or expanded at runtime.
- 4) **Attested Composition Agreement.** All honest parties provision data only after verifying the same μ and a manifest σ signed by a key pk_G that is itself bound to μ via attestation. No party can cause execution under a different component composition or policy without detection by honest connectors.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

This section presents the implementation of the *Two-Way Confidential Virtual Machine*. The prototype demonstrates how the architecture described in Section IV operates in practice and how its components interact within a working system. Section VI-A discusses the implementation details of the various 2cVM components, and Section VI-B outlines the full workflow of a 2cVM run.

All experiments were conducted on Ubuntu 25.04 with Linux kernel 6.14, where SEV-SNP support is fully integrated

into both the host and the guest. The host uses QEMU 9.2.1 with SEV-SNP enabled through standard configuration options and firmware built according to AMD's guidelines [2]. Within the guest, the required user-space components are installed to support attestation, composition, and execution: the `snpguest` [46] utility for obtaining SEV-SNP attestation reports, the `WAC` [8] composition tool for producing composite WebAssembly binaries from the *Commitment Manifest*-defined `.wac` description, the `wasmtime` [9] runtime for executing WebAssembly components, `wasmm-tools` [7] for checking WIT imports, and the *Attestation Agent*, which coordinates the 2cVM lifecycle and invokes these tools. The agent is deployed as a `systemd` service and starts automatically when the VM boots.

To prevent data persistence beyond the VM's lifetime, all runtime operations occur within a temporary in-memory filesystem [51]. The directories used for component binaries (`/deps/`), input data (`/data/`), and output artifacts (`/output/`) exist only in volatile memory and are destroyed when the VM shuts down.

A. COMPONENTS

The implementation builds on two complementary isolation layers. The first layer uses AMD's SEV-SNP Confidential Virtual Machine technology as the confidential-computing substrate for protecting the 2cVM's memory and execution state from the **untrusted host**. On top of this, the WebAssembly Component Model provides a language-agnostic sandbox for isolating and composing the code contributed by each participant. Together, these layers enforce mutual confidentiality between all parties involved.

The **Attestation Agent** is implemented in Python using FastAPI and exposes a set of endpoints that govern the 2cVM lifecycle: locking the *Commitment Manifest*, attesting the environment, admitting and validating artifacts, orchestrating execution, and returning results. Communication with the runtime (`wasmtime`) and attestation utility (`snpguest`) occurs via subprocess calls, which simplifies the implementation and preserves modularity. In a production deployment, these components could be linked directly to reduce process overhead and further shrink the trusted computing base.

The **Commitment Manifest** is realized as a JSON document that encodes the relations between participants, data assets, and code components in a machine-readable form. Each participant entry contains a human-readable name and a stable identifier that is used by external governance or identity systems. Components are listed with an explicit link to the participant that owns or supplies them and a list of permitted WIT interface imports. A dedicated `composition` field carries the WebAssembly Component Model composition that instantiates these components and exports the resulting interface. Data items are defined as named inputs associated with a specific participant, and a separate permissions section ties everything together: for each component, it specifies which data items may be accessed and which outputs may

be produced, including the function that generates the output and the participant to whom it is delivered. Optional metadata fields, such as transfer or transaction identifiers, allow the same *Commitment Manifest* to serve as a bridge to external data-space protocols.

External participants interact with the *Attestation Agent* through **Connectors**. Each organization operates its own trusted Connector, which manages communication with the 2cVM on behalf of that participant. The Connectors use data-space-compatible message formats such as W3C Verifiable Credentials to maintain interoperability with existing data-space infrastructures while exchanging code, data, and configuration information.

For simplicity, the prototype omits transport-level encryption and endpoint authentication. In a production system, the agent would operate over TLS with identity-bound authentication such as OIDC. Integrating Remote Attestation–TLS (RA-TLS) [27] would allow attestation evidence to be embedded in the TLS handshake, creating verifiable, secure channels between participants. These extensions are considered out of scope for the proof-of-concept but are discussed in Section X on future work.

B. TWO-WAY CONFIDENTIAL VM EXECUTION FLOW

The 2cVM workflow proceeds in three sequential stages that collectively establish trust, admit artifacts, and execute the declared computation. Each stage is realized through a set of API endpoints exposed by the *Attestation Agent*. Figures 2 and 3 provide, respectively, a schematic overview of these stages and a detailed sequence diagram.

Stage 1: Locking the *Commitment Manifest*

The first stage establishes the configuration and governance of the 2cVM instance. A participating organization begins by sending the negotiated *Commitment Manifest* to the agent's **/lock** endpoint.

Upon receiving the *Commitment Manifest*, the agent checks whether a lock already exists in memory. If the instance is already locked, the request is rejected with an HTTP 400 response, enforcing the manifest's immutability. Otherwise, it is serialized to the in-memory filesystem and is loaded into two thread-safe state objects: the *ThreadSafeCommitmentManifest*, representing the active configuration, and the *ThreadSafePartySubmissionState*, which tracks each artifact's submission status. From this point onward, the agent interprets all subsequent requests in accordance with the locked *Commitment Manifest*, and the 2cVM's configuration cannot be altered without a full reset.

Stage 2: Attestation and Artifact Submission

Once the *Commitment Manifest* has been locked, participants must verify that the system is operating on genuine confidential hardware and that the locked configuration matches the agreed-upon parameters, thereby providing proof of both 2cVM isolation layers. This verification is performed via the **/attestation** endpoint.

To prevent replay attacks, the attestation endpoint accepts a hexadecimal nonce as input. When invoked, the agent first ensures that a *signing key pair* exists within the in-memory filesystem, generating one if necessary. It then constructs the attestation challenge by hashing both the provided nonce and the public part of the *signing key pair*, concatenating them as $\text{SHA-256}(\text{Nonce})\|\text{SHA-256}(\text{PK}_{\text{signing}})$. This value is passed as `user_data` to the `snpguest` binary, which requests a hardware-signed attestation report from the CPU (AL1-AL4). The report cryptographically binds the platform state, the nonce, and the *signing key pair*, extending them into the TCB.

If a *Commitment Manifest* is already locked, the agent additionally signs its serialized contents with the *signing key pair*, creating a *commitment attestation*.

The resulting JSON response includes:

- the base64-encoded SEV-SNP attestation report,
- the serialized and signed *Commitment Manifest*, and
- the public part of the *signing key pair*.

Participants can verify the platform attestation against AMD's endorsement keys and known measurements of the components in AL1-AL4. The *Commitment Manifest* signature can be checked against the included public *signing key*. This guarantees that the computation environment and policy are authentic and immutable throughout the VM's lifetime.

Once attestation has succeeded, participants may submit their declared artifacts through the **/application** endpoint. Each submission consists of a JSON structure containing a participant identifier, the artifact's manifest ID, and a base64-encoded or JSON body. In this proof-of-concept, no cryptographic verification of the identifier is performed.

Submissions are validated against the locked *Commitment Manifest*. For artifacts of type `component`, the agent decodes the binary and places it in a quarantine area. The agent inspects the component's declared WASI imports and compares them against the permissions declared in the *Commitment Manifest* for that participant. If the imports do not match the expected values, the submission is rejected and the binary is discarded. This validation step ensures that any authority to interact with external resources, such as filesystem access required to produce output artifacts, is explicitly declared through the component's interface and auditable prior to execution. Only after this validation succeeds is the component admitted to the in-memory filesystem under `/deps/< participant>/`. For artifacts of type `data`, the content is serialized and stored directly under `/data/< participant>/`. Each successful submission updates the *Party Submission State*.

Stage 3: Runtime Orchestration and Result Retrieval

The third stage is triggered automatically once all submissions have been received. The agent composes the workload according to the composition defined in the *Commitment Manifest*, generating a WebAssembly composition file (`.wac`) that encodes the declared component dependencies. This file is then passed to the `wac` CLI, which produces a composite WebAssembly binary that

FIGURE 2. The different stages in the 2cVM architecture: 1) locking negotiated *Commitment Manifest* to 2cVM, 2) attestation of the platform and *Commitment Manifest* & upload of sensitive information, 3) code execution and distribution of output.

integrates all participant components within the manifest-defined structure. The resulting composite is executed using *wasmtime*, with read-write access to the */data* and */output* directories mounted as isolated capabilities within the runtime in accordance with the *Commitment Manifest*. Execution occurs asynchronously in a detached subprocess, ensuring that the agent remains responsive to API requests throughout runtime operation.

Authorized participants may later retrieve computation results through the */application/result* endpoint. The endpoint expects a participant identifier as a query parameter, validates it against the output permissions defined in the *Commitment Manifest*, and returns only the data explicitly authorized for that participant. Text outputs are returned directly, while binary outputs are base64-encoded.

This final stage enforces the end-to-end confidentiality guarantees of the 2cVM. The runtime operates strictly within the bounds of the attested *Commitment Manifest*, data movement follows only the permitted channels, and results are released exclusively to authorized recipients.

VII. EVALUATION

This section assesses the performance and practicality of the Two-Way Confidential VM. The evaluation is organized around four complementary benchmarks, each targeting a distinct aspect of 2cVM’s behavior and collectively spanning workloads with distinct computational profiles to demonstrate generalizability across workloads.. Section VII-B first contextualizes 2cVM against fully homomorphic encryption to establish the macro-level efficiency case. Sections VII-C and VII-D then examine overhead layer by layer, using a compute-bound arithmetic workload and a memory-intensive

SQLite workload respectively. Section VII-E evaluates an ONNX inference workload, exposing an important interaction between the two isolation layers under an inference workload that combines irregular memory access with compute-intensive floating-point operations. Section VII-F examines the attestation subsystem under concurrent load, which is a scalability property that the other benchmarks do not exercise. Finally, Section VII-G evaluates the architecture against concrete adversarial actions within the defined security model.

A. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

All experiments were conducted on a dedicated server equipped with an AMD EPYC 8124P 16-core processor supporting SEV-SNP, 192 GB of RAM, and NVMe storage. The host runs Ubuntu 25.04 with a Linux 6.14 kernel, which provides SEV-SNP host support out of the box. Both the regular VM and the confidential VM are managed by a KVM-enabled QEMU hypervisor (v9.2.1). Each VM was provisioned with 512 MB of RAM and 2 virtual CPU cores for the arithmetic and FHE workload and 4096 MB of RAM and 1 virtual CPU core for the other workloads. The guest disk image contains a clean installation of Ubuntu 25.04 with a Linux 6.14 kernel, providing native SEV-SNP guest support, verified using the AMD *snpghost* tool [46]. The VMs were booted with custom AMD virtual firmware built according to the manufacturer’s instructions [2]. Each benchmark is evaluated across four configurations: native execution in a standard VM, native execution in a SEV-SNP confidential VM, Wasm component model in a standard VM, and Wasm component model in a SEV-SNP confidential VM. This structure isolates the contribution of each isolation layer

FIGURE 3. Sequence of a nominal 2cVM execution flow with two participants.

independently and in combination. Benchmarks, data, and analysis scripts are provided as public artifacts [42].

B. COMPARISON WITH FULLY HOMOMORPHIC ENCRYPTION

To contextualize 2cVM’s performance profile, it is first compared against fully homomorphic encryption, which offers the strongest form of data confidentiality in use but at high computational cost. On its own, FHE protects input data against the compute provider, yet it does not provide the multi-party code and data collaboration or mutual distrust semantics that 2cVM targets. However, any practical collaborative system built around FHE or multi-key FHE would still have its runtime dominated by the underlying homomorphic evaluation. The comparison therefore focuses on the confidentiality of the compute layer using a matrix-vector multiplication workload, a fundamental linear algebra operation used throughout machine learning

and data analytics. The matrix has fixed square dimensions with a matching vector length, yielding a compute-intensive task with predictable memory access patterns ideal for isolating CPU overhead. Three variants are evaluated:

- 1) **FHE baseline.** An open-source [32] matrix vector multiplication implementation which uses the OpenFHE framework [35] (Python interface, which internally relies on optimized C/C++ routines). This implementation performs encrypted matrix–vector multiplication using homomorphic addition and multiplication over ciphertexts, serving as a reference for cryptographic confidentiality. Each iteration of this benchmark performs the multiplication 10 times and averages the time for each operation within an iteration.
- 2) **Native reference.** Implemented in Rust, compiled with `-release` optimizations using the stable toolchain (`cargo build -release`). This variant executes directly within a standard virtual machine and serves

as the unencrypted baseline for both performance and correctness comparison. Each iteration of this benchmark performs the multiplication 200.000 times and averages the time for each operation within an iteration.

- 3) **Component model variant.** The same Rust logic compiled to WebAssembly using the WASI-Preview2 target (`wasm32-wasip2`). This version executes within the 2cVM’s WebAssembly component model runtime (`wasmtime`), enabling fine-grained sandboxing and capability-based I/O isolation. It contains two components: a caller and an executor. The caller generates the matrix and passes it to the executor once, who then performs the computation a number of times and eventually returns the result once. Each iteration of this benchmark performs the multiplication 200.000 times and averages the time for each operation within an iteration.

Each variant iteration was measured ten times with random matrices. The average and sample standard deviation per configuration were computed, and the ratio of the averages was formed to obtain the relative overhead. The reported \pm values are propagated standard deviations obtained by applying standard error propagation to the ratio. Matrix and vector initialization happens outside the timed execution window and is not part of the benchmark. The comparison uses a 128×128 matrix multiplied by a vector of length 128.

FHE execution consistently runs about 10^5 x slower than 2cVM across our benchmark. Figure 4 illustrates this difference on a log scale. Although specialized acceleration techniques such as GPU, FPGA, or ASIC implementation can narrow this gap in certain tightly optimized workloads, they remain applicable only to specific primitives and do not eliminate FHE’s fundamental performance barrier. Even with

FIGURE 4. Comparison of 128×128 matrix–vector multiplication runtimes, showing that FHE introduces roughly a 10^5 x overhead relative to the 2cVM solution.

such acceleration, end-to-end applications remain several orders of magnitude slower than plaintext computation [19].

While these findings highlight the efficiency advantage of 2cVM, the benchmark input size (128×128) is relatively small and therefore slightly biases the comparison in favor of the FHE implementation. One of 2cVM’s two isolation layers, the WebAssembly component model, still incurs non-negligible overhead when transferring data across component boundaries. As matrix dimensions grow, the computational cost of the multiplication increases quadratically, whereas the data-transfer cost grows only linearly. Consequently, the relative overhead of data movement rapidly diminishes as input size increases. Figure 5 visualizes this trend, showing how transfer overhead becomes negligible as input size increases. This transfer cost is a function of data volume and exchange frequency across component boundaries, not of participant count; a deployment with many participants exchanging small payloads infrequently will incur lower transfer overhead than one with few participants exchanging large data volumes repeatedly. As the WebAssembly Component Model is rapidly evolving, these data-transfer overheads should diminish over time as new and improved ways of sharing data between components are introduced.

FIGURE 5. Impact of the problem size on the relative performance of the WASM Component Model with a fitted trend line. Overhead is dominated by data transfer between components and trends to near zero for large inputs.

C. LAYER-WISE OVERHEAD: ARITHMETIC WORKLOADS

2cVM employs a dual-isolation-layer strategy. The inner layer, provided by the WebAssembly Component model, prevents exfiltration by malicious code. The outer Confidential Computing layer protects the system against infiltration by the host. This section evaluates each layer’s overhead independently using the matrix-vector multiplication workload introduced in Section VII-B, which is CPU-bound, memory-resident, and syscall-light, conditions that represent a best case for 2cVM overhead. Table 1 provides an overview of the relative performance overhead of 2cVM and its two layers compared to a native execution; FHE is included again as a reference.

TABLE 1. Overhead per technology relative to native execution (2cVM = WASM component + confidential VM).

Technology	Mechanism	Overhead (%)
2cVM	Two-layer isolation	6.18 (± 0.20)
WASM Component	WASI sandbox	5.36 (± 0.19)
Confidential VM	SEV-SNP	0.77 (± 0.16)
FHE	Ciphertext computation	4.18×10^5 ($\pm 6.32 \times 10^3$)

1) WeBASsembly COMPONENT MODEL LAYER

The inner layer of 2cVM introduces isolation of each party's data and code through the WebAssembly (WASM) component model, which enables composable modules with capability-based security. The runtime cost of this abstraction is evaluated relative to native execution.

The results show a mean overhead of $5.36(\pm 0.19)\%$ for a 512×512 matrix. As mentioned in section VII-B a good part of this overhead can be attributed to the way the Component Model handles data sharing between components and diminishes with increasing input sizes. The remaining percentage points can be attributed to the sandbox itself requiring bounds checking for memory access and allocations of new pages by the runtime. Figure 6 shows a detailed graph of the performance overhead.

FIGURE 6. Impact of the WebAssembly Component isolation layer of 2cVM on execution time. Results show a mean overhead of $5.36(\pm 0.19)\%$.

Despite this, the overhead is modest relative to the security and portability benefits provided by the component model. The WASM layer enforces strict module boundaries, fine-grained capability-based I/O, and language independence; all properties difficult to replicate in native code. Within 2cVM, this layer effectively compartmentalizes untrusted or third-party code while maintaining computational performance.

2) CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING LAYER

This section evaluates the overhead introduced by executing the same componentized WASM workload inside a

confidential virtual machine enforced by SEV-SNP. In this configuration, both the caller and the executor components remain unchanged; the only difference lies in the underlying hardware isolation and encrypted memory model.

The results, relative to the non-confidential VM, show an average overhead of less than 1%. Figure 7 shows a detailed graph. This negligible difference aligns with expectations given the characteristics of our workload: the matrix-vector multiplication benchmark is CPU-bound, memory-resident, and syscall-light. All computation occurs within user space, with minimal host-guest interaction and virtually no external I/O. Under such conditions, SEV-SNP's memory-encryption and integrity-verification engines operate nearly transparently.

FIGURE 7. Impact of the confidential VM isolation layer of 2cVM on execution time. Results show a mean overhead of $0.77(\pm 0.16)\%$.

This result reflects the baseline performance cost inherent to encrypted memory access within confidential VMs. Studies that evaluated I/O-intensive or syscall-heavy workloads, such as OLTP databases, key-value stores, and filesystem benchmarks, observe an increased slowdown once execution interacts with untrusted components of the host [39]. The main sources of this additional overhead are repeated VM exits for emulated I/O, bounce buffering between encrypted guest memory and shared host buffers, and, on newer hardware, integrity checks on memory pages via the Reverse Map Table (RMP). These mechanisms add extra data copies, address translations, and synchronization events to each I/O operation, which amplifies latency and CPU utilization [52]. The arithmetic benchmark avoids all of these paths.

Combining layer VII-C1 and VII-C2, the holistic overhead of the Two-Way Confidential VM is demonstrated to be $6.18(\pm 0.20)\%$ (Figure 8).

D. MEMORY EVALUATION: SQLite

The arithmetic benchmark in Section VII-C isolates CPU-bound computation with predictable memory access.

FIGURE 8. Impact of the full 2cVM isolation on execution time. Results show a mean overhead of 6.18 (± 0.20)%.

To evaluate 2cVM’s performance on qualitatively different memory behavior, this section examines an in-memory SQLite database exercising bulk sequential writes, random indexed reads, and full table scans. These patterns differ fundamentally in their memory access behavior: bulk inserts and indexed point reads involve irregular memory access where each address depends on the result of the previous one, while full table scans access memory in a largely sequential order. The random access pattern is representative of many real collaborative workloads, such as record matching, provenance lookup, and policy evaluation, where data access is irregular and cannot benefit from hardware prefetching.

1) BENCHMARK DESIGN

The benchmark is implemented as a Rust library exposing a single function, `request(query: String)`, which dispatches SQL strings to a persistent in-memory SQLite connection held in thread-local storage. The table is declared `WITHOUT ROWID`, ensuring that every point lookup traverses the index by repeated key comparison and maximizing irregular memory access behavior.

Three sub-benchmarks are run sequentially against an in-memory database:

- 1) **Bulk inserts.** Five million rows of the form `user_i` are inserted within a single explicit transaction. Batching all inserts into one transaction is essential to suppress per-statement flush overhead and isolate runtime cost. The metric is inserts per second over the full transaction.
- 2) **Random point reads.** Two hundred thousand indexed lookups are issued using the deterministic scatter pattern $idx = (i \times 97) \bmod 5\,000\,000$. Because 97 is coprime with 5×10^6 , the sequence forms a permutation of the full keyspace over a complete period, ensuring the 200 000 samples are uniformly distributed without a random number generator.

- 3) **Full table scans.** Five sequential `SELECT *` queries are issued over all five million rows. The result handler counts rows without deserializing column values, isolating traversal overhead from serialization cost. The metric is seconds per scan.

Each sub-benchmark is preceded by a warm-up query to avoid penalising cold cache effects. The same four configurations used in Section VII-C are evaluated: native execution in a non-confidential VM, native execution in a SEV-SNP VM, Wasm component model in a non-confidential VM, and Wasm component model in a SEV-SNP VM.

2) RESULTS

Figure 9 shows throughput for each sub-benchmark, normalised to the native non-confidential baseline.

The results exhibit the same two-factor structure observed in Section VII-C. SEV-SNP introduces approximately 3% overhead across all three workloads. While higher than the sub-1% observed for the arithmetic benchmark, this remains modest even for these more realistic, memory-intensive workloads, and is not the dominant source of overhead. Wasm, by contrast, imposes consistent but workload-dependent overhead: bulk inserts and point reads run at 48–51% of native throughput (approximately $2\times$ slowdown), while full scans run at 68% of native throughput (approximately $1.5\times$ slowdown). In all cases, Wasm overhead is independent of whether SEV-SNP is enabled, confirming that the two isolation layers do not interact and that the bottleneck lies entirely within the Wasm runtime.

The asymmetry between point reads ($2\times$) and full scans ($1.5\times$) is consistent with a performance penalty that scales with the degree of irregular memory access in the workload.

3) WASM MEMORY OVERHEAD: SEQUENTIAL VS. IRREGULAR ACCESS

Two targeted memory benchmarks disambiguate the source of the Wasm overhead.

a: SEQUENTIAL BANDWIDTH

Table 2 shows STREAM [29] results for native and Wasm builds. Sequential memory bandwidth under Wasm is not degraded; across all four kernels, the Wasm build matches or marginally exceeds native throughput. This rules out memory bandwidth as the cause of the SQL slowdown and establishes that the Wasm runtime does not impede sequential memory operations.

TABLE 2. STREAM memory bandwidth (best rate, MB/s), mean \pm std over 5 runs. Wasm sequential bandwidth is within measurement noise of native.

Kernel	Native (MB/s)	Wasm (MB/s)	Ratio
Copy	26,173 \pm 492	26,835 \pm 466	1.03 \times
Scale	30,324 \pm 263	31,993 \pm 564	1.06 \times
Add	30,778 \pm 173	32,557 \pm 716	1.06 \times
Triad	31,062 \pm 190	31,875 \pm 580	1.03 \times

SQLite-in-memory benchmark: Wasm vs. Native, Non-SEV-SNP vs. SEV-SNP

FIGURE 9. SQLite in-memory benchmark throughput for bulk inserts, indexed point reads, and full table scans. Values are normalised to native execution in a non-confidential VM. SEV-SNP introduces less than 3% overhead across all workloads. The Wasm execution layer imposes approximately 2x overhead on write and random-access workloads and 1.5x on sequential scans.

b: RANDOM-ACCESS LATENCY

Figure 10 shows pointer-chasing latency as a function of working set size, measured using ram_bench [14]. For working sets fitting within L1 and L2 cache, Wasm latency is 2–3x native. In the L3 region this grows to approximately 4x. Once the working set exceeds the L3 cache, Wasm latency diverges sharply: in the DRAM regime the overhead reaches roughly 13x native on average.

FIGURE 10. Random-access latency as a function of working set size for native and Wasm component model builds. Latencies are within 2–3x for working sets contained in L1 or L2 cache. Beyond the L3 boundary the Wasm curve diverges sharply, reaching around 13x native latency. Vertical dashed lines mark indicate L1, L2, and L3 VM cache boundaries.

These results show that 2cVM’s Wasm overhead on memory-intensive workloads is determined not by the amount of memory accessed but by the access pattern. Workloads dominated by irregular, pointer-chasing traversal, as is common in tree-structured data stores, graph algorithms,

and sparse lookups, will experience overhead in the range observed here, while workloads with predominantly sequential access patterns are unaffected, as confirmed by the STREAM results.

E. INFERENCE WORKLOADS: ONNX MNIST

The previous sections establish that SEV-SNP overhead is workload-dependent and that Wasm overhead is driven by memory access patterns. This section introduces a third dimension: how the two isolation layers interact under an inference workload that combines irregular memory access with compute-intensive floating-point operations, making it a more representative proxy for real collaborative machine learning pipelines.

1) BENCHMARK DESIGN

The benchmark executes ONNX-based MNIST classification compiled into three variants:

- 1) **Native.** A standard native binary compiled from the ONNX runtime, executing 5000 classification runs on a hard-coded MNIST bitmap.
- 2) **Native (fast-math).** The same native binary compiled with aggressive floating-point optimizations enabled (e.g., `-ffast-math`).
- 3) **WebAssembly.** The workload compiled to WebAssembly and executed using the Wasmtime runtime, using ahead-of-time compiled bytecode (`.cwasm`) to minimize runtime compilation overhead.

The fast-math variant is included to illustrate the performance impact of compiler-level floating-point optimizations that are unavailable in WebAssembly, which

mandates deterministic floating-point semantics. Each binary is executed using hyperfine [38], repeated ten times, with the mean execution time reported. Both VM configurations defined in Section VII-A are evaluated.

2) RESULTS

Table 3 summarizes the mean execution times. Two effects are visible. First, SEV-SNP imposes a 20.4% overhead on the native binary and 16.4% on the fast-math variant, significantly higher than observed for the arithmetic and SQLite benchmarks. This reflects the more diverse memory access and compute patterns of an inference workload, which stress the hardware memory protection mechanisms more than the previous benchmarks. Second, Wasm introduces a 12.1% overhead relative to native in the non-SEV-SNP environment, but SEV-SNP adds only a further 2.0% on top. Since the Wasm runtime already constrains execution, the marginal cost of hardware memory protection is absorbed and the two layers do not accumulate linearly.

TABLE 3. Mean execution time for the ONNX inference benchmark across different execution environments.

Workload	Native VM (s)	SEV-SNP VM (s)
ONNX (native)	2.404 ± 0.005	2.894 ± 0.007
ONNX (fast-math)	1.281 ± 0.002	1.492 ± 0.003
ONNX (WebAssembly)	2.696 ± 0.007	2.750 ± 0.012

The fast-math variant illustrates an additional tradeoff. The performance gap between native and fast-math reflects optimizations, such as reassociation of floating-point operations and relaxed IEEE 754 compliance, that are fundamentally incompatible with WebAssembly’s deterministic floating-point semantics. The performance difference is therefore not overhead introduced by the runtime, but a consequence of a deliberate design choice in the WebAssembly specification.

F. CONCURRENT MULTI-PARTY ATTESTATION

Remote attestation is a core primitive in 2cVM: every participant performs exactly one attestation before submitting artifacts, making total attestation cost a direct function of participant count. Execution overhead, by contrast, is not governed by participant count but by data volume crossing component boundaries and the memory access patterns of the workloads, as the preceding benchmarks demonstrate. Scaling participant count with a fixed workload would therefore not expose meaningful variation beyond what those benchmarks already characterize. The attestation phase is where participant count has an unambiguous, direct effect, and if the underlying /dev/sev-guest interface serializes requests, concurrent attestation becomes the binding scalability constraint in multi-party deployments. This section empirically characterizes the latency of that interface under concurrent load.

1) BENCHMARK DESIGN

The benchmark launches multiple worker threads within the guest VM. Each thread opens its own file descriptor to the /dev/sev-guest device and repeatedly issues the SNP_GET_REPORT ioctl to request an attestation report. To ensure true concurrent invocation, all threads synchronize on a barrier before each request, causing the ioctl calls to be issued as simultaneously as possible. Each request is timed using a monotonic clock, recording the duration of the ioctl call from invocation to completion.

For each repetition, the completion times of all concurrent requests are ordered to determine their queue position. The first request to complete corresponds to the effective service time of a single attestation operation, while subsequent positions reflect the latency experienced by requests waiting behind earlier ones.

2) RESULTS

Figure 11 shows the distribution of attestation latency as a function of queue position when ten concurrent threads request reports simultaneously. The results exhibit a clear linear increase across queue positions: the first request completes in approximately 4.4–4.7 ms, while the tenth completes around 44 ms, with each successive request adding roughly 4.4 ms of additional latency. This closely matches the intrinsic service time of a single report generation.

FIGURE 11. Attestation latency vs. queue position for 10 concurrent threads issuing SNP_GET_REPORT ioctls simultaneously. Latency scales linearly at ≈4.4 ms per position, consistent with strict serialization at the /dev/sev-guest interface. Red bars indicate the median; blue points show individual observations.

The low variance within each queue position confirms that the dominant cost arises from deterministic service time rather than scheduling noise or thread contention. The /dev/sev-guest device effectively operates as a single-service queue: concurrent requests are serialized, independent of how many file descriptors or threads are used. This limitation is inherent to the attestation interface itself and is independent of higher-level software stacks. Any 2cVM deployment with many concurrent participants must therefore

account for this linear scaling when estimating attestation latency. Although it is not possible to parallelize this, it might be possible to instead use a vTPM for performing attestation in a more scalable manner. Future work will investigate using a vTPM for evidence attestation.

G. SECURITY EVALUATION

This section evaluates the 2cVM architecture against the four security goals defined in Section V, considering concrete adversarial actions within the security model. The evaluation considers the design of the architecture and its specific instantiation combining AMD SEV-SNP with the WebAssembly Component Model. Limitations of the proof-of-concept implementation and the underlying confidential computing platform are addressed in Section VIII.

1) HOST ISOLATION

An adversary controlling the host hypervisor cannot read or modify the in-memory state of the 2cVM instance: AMD SEV-SNP encrypts and integrity-protects guest memory with respect to the host, and any attempted modification is detected by the hardware. By design, all runtime operations, including component binaries, input data, and output artifacts, are stored exclusively in a volatile in-memory filesystem and destroyed when the VM shuts down, ensuring that no sensitive data persists beyond the VM's lifetime in a form accessible to the host.

2) MEASURED LAUNCH INTEGRITY

An adversary attempting to launch the VM with a modified kernel, runtime, or Attestation Agent binary will produce a different measurement μ . Because μ is bound to the signing key via the attestation report, the manifest signature returned to connectors will be associated with a different platform state, causing connector verification to fail. A full deployment covering AL1 through AL4 achieves this by cryptographically measuring the hardware platform, firmware, guest kernel, runtime, and Attestation Agent via a vTPM-based measured boot sequence. The Attestation Agent extends this at the policy level by signing the Commitment Manifest with a key pair generated inside the guest, extending cryptographic coverage to the governing policy itself.

3) COMPONENT ISOLATION AND POLICY ENFORCEMENT

An adversary supplying a malicious component that attempts to exceed the permissions granted in σ is stopped before execution. Submitted components are first placed in quarantine, where the attestation agent inspects their declared WIT interfaces and associated WASI imports. These imports are compared against the permissions assigned to the component in the Commitment Manifest. If the component requests capabilities not authorized in σ , the binary is discarded and the submission rejected prior to execution.

If an adversarial component is admitted legitimately, it still cannot access the internal state of other components. The WebAssembly Component Model enforces per-component

linear memory isolation by design, and inter-component communication is restricted to explicitly declared interfaces. Consequently, if σ does not authorize an interface through which C_i may communicate with C_j , the runtime provides no program-visible mechanism by which C_j can obtain information about C_i .

It is important to note that this isolation guarantee is one of access control, not information-flow control. The Commitment Manifest and runtime enforcement prevent a component from opening unauthorized channels, but they impose no semantic constraints on the content carried through authorized ones. A malicious component that is legitimately admitted with authorized output capabilities could in principle encode and exfiltrate sensitive information through those outputs. Preventing such covert exfiltration would require semantic constraints on channel content, for example, through output-filter components interposed between producers and connectors, as discussed in Section X.

Finally, an adversary attempting to leak information through external outputs is constrained by the same policy. Components may only emit data through WASI capabilities that were authorized during admission, and external connectors can retrieve result artifacts only if the Commitment Manifest explicitly assigns those outputs to them. Consequently, any observable output channel must be declared in σ , and cannot be introduced or expanded by a malicious component at runtime.

4) ATTESTED COMPOSITION AGREEMENT

An adversary attempting to substitute the Commitment Manifest after locking, or to replay a stale attestation report, is defeated by two independent mechanisms. First, the lock is immutable: any subsequent attempt to replace the manifest is rejected by the Attestation Agent. Second, each attestation flow requires a fresh nonce supplied by the connector, making replay of a previous attestation report detectable. The agent signs the locked manifest with a key pair generated inside the guest, and the attestation report cryptographically binds the platform measurement μ to that public key. A connector independently verifies that the report is genuine, that the signing key is bound to μ , and that the manifest matches what was agreed. No party can cause execution under a different component composition or policy without producing a different μ , which fails verification by honest connectors.

Finally, it is worth noting that none of the four security goals can be violated by a crash or forced termination of the VM. An adversary able to kill or crash the 2cVM instance can prevent computation from completing, but the confidentiality and integrity of provisioned data and code are unaffected: all runtime state exists exclusively in volatile memory and is destroyed on shutdown. This reduces the impact of such events to denial of service, which is explicitly permitted by the security model. Availability guarantees are therefore orthogonal to the security goals defined here and are discussed separately in Section VIII.

VIII. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

This section discusses the limitations of the proof-of-concept implementation and the underlying Confidential Computing and WebAssembly layers.

A. 2cVM PROTOTYPE

The current implementation illustrates the technical feasibility of the 2cVM architecture but is not intended for production deployments. It has not been formally audited, and security guarantees are bounded by the security model defined in Section V.

1) PARTICIPANT AUTHENTICATION

The prototype does not perform cryptographic verification of participant identifiers on artifact submission. Admission-time enforcement therefore relies on the confidentiality of the communication channel rather than verified identity. A production deployment would require identity-bound authentication, for example through OIDC, and ideally RA-TLS to embed attestation evidence directly into the transport layer, creating a verifiable and authenticated channel between participants and the Attestation Agent.

2) LACK OF vTPM SUPPORT

The current prototype uses CPU-based evidence gathered from SEV-SNP itself. However, many operating systems implement AL4 attestation using vTPMs. On such operating systems, our solution would not correctly attest AL4, because it only uses the CPU-based evidence for attestation, instead of also including vTPM evidence. Future work should make the attestation mechanism of our attestation agent flexible so that it can choose to also include vTPM-based evidence in the remote attestation flow, for operating systems that support it.

3) NO RECOVERY FROM MID-EXECUTION FAILURE

A failure during execution produces no output and provides no recovery mechanism. In such cases the confidential VM should be destroyed by the provider and participants should initiate a new transaction. Data retention and cleanup policies based on such failure scenarios are outside the scope of this work.

4) AVAILABILITY

The security model does not include availability guarantees. A malicious host can refuse to start the VM or interfere with network access. This does not violate any of the defined security goals but means that 2cVM provides no protection against denial of service at the infrastructure level.

B. WEBASSEMBLY

1) SINGLE WASI INTERFACE PER COMPOSITION

The WebAssembly Component Model currently does not yet support assigning the same WASI interface to multiple components independently within a single composition. In practice this means only one component can hold a

given WASI interface, such as filesystem access. The agent enforces this through the Commitment Manifest, bounding the interface to specific files or directories, but this limits the flexibility of multi-party compositions where multiple components require the same interface. This can be resolved using `wasi-virt` [6], which virtualizes WASI interfaces and allows per-component isolation of shared interfaces. Moreover, this limitation is set to be removed in WASI preview 3, with its support for named interface imports. This will allow multiple distinct imports of the same interface in a single component.

2) CONSTANT-TIME EXECUTION

WebAssembly currently cannot guarantee constant-time execution, making components vulnerable to timing-based side-channel attacks on cryptographic operations. Research on constant-time WebAssembly exists both for compilation and validation [21], [43], but it is not yet standardized or enforced by mainstream runtimes.

3) PORTABILITY OF EXISTING SOFTWARE

Compiling existing software to the WebAssembly Component Model is not always straightforward. Support is strongest for lower-level languages such as Rust and C, while higher-level languages have more limited or experimental support. This is an active area of development within the WebAssembly standards community [48].

C. CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

1) MEMORY-ONLY PROTECTION

Confidential computing protects data in use by encrypting guest memory. Data written to disk is not covered by this protection. Care must be taken to ensure that no sensitive data is persisted to disk during execution; the guest disk image should be integrity-protected and, where possible, encrypted with a key held by the image provider to prevent host interference.

2) REVOCATION AFTER DATA RELEASE

Once output data has been released to an authorized participant, revocation is not possible. Data release only occurs after successful attestation, but if the attestation state were to change after release, for example due to a firmware update altering the measurement, previously released data cannot be recalled. This is a general limitation of attestation-based systems and remains an open research problem.

3) HARDWARE VULNERABILITIES

Like all confidential computing platforms, AMD SEV-SNP is subject to hardware-level vulnerabilities. Two recent attacks are worth highlighting for their impact on 2cVM. TEE.fail [11] enables ciphertext side-channel attacks that can leak private keys during cryptographic signing operations via a DDR5 memory interposer. AMD's attestation signing happens in a separate chip and does not collapse, but any

cryptographic operation inside the guest potentially leaks a private key. BatteringRAM [12] allows replay of memory pages via a DDR4 memory interposer, enabling an attacker to bypass AMD's attestation measurements by replaying another confidential VM's state. Both attacks require the host owner to be actively malicious at an organizational level, a compromised host system alone is not sufficient. For this reason, manufacturers consider these attacks out of scope, though they remain actively exploitable.

While the prototype uses AMD SEV-SNP, the 2cVM architecture is designed to be agnostic to the underlying confidential computing substrate. Migrating to a more secure platform as one becomes available requires no architectural changes. Until hardware vulnerabilities in current platforms are resolved, deployments involving cryptographic operations inside the guest should carefully consider the implications of these attacks within their specific adversary model.

IX. CONCLUSION

This work presented the concept, design, and evaluation of the Two-Way Confidential Virtual Machine, a system that combines hardware-backed isolation with language-level sandboxing to protect both data and code in collaborative computing environments. By extending the guarantees of traditional Confidential VMs with an inner WebAssembly isolation layer, 2cVM prevents not only infiltration from a malicious host but also exfiltration by untrusted code running within the same confidential environment. All computation is governed by a Commitment Manifest that is cryptographically bound to the attested platform state, making the governing policy immutable and independently verifiable throughout the VM's lifetime.

Experimental evaluation across four benchmark classes shows that the layered design achieves strong security without multiplicative performance penalties. The two isolation layers do not accumulate linearly: once a workload executes inside the Wasm sandbox, the marginal cost of enabling SEV-SNP hardware protection is small. Overhead is workload-dependent rather than fixed: SEV-SNP remains modest across all tested workloads, while Wasm overhead is governed primarily by memory access pattern, ranging from negligible for sequential workloads to approximately $2\times$ for irregular, pointer-chasing access patterns. The attestation subsystem introduces an orthogonal scalability constraint, with request latency scaling linearly under concurrent load due to serialization at the hardware interface level.

Overall, 2cVM demonstrates that hardware attestation and modular, capability-based sandboxing can be combined to enable secure, auditable, and efficient multi-party computation. It operationalizes zero-trust principles within confidential computing environments, ensuring that trust is never assumed but continuously established through attestation and manifest-based governance, while remaining compatible with existing data-sharing frameworks such as data spaces.

X. FUTURE WORK

A. OUTPUT-FILTER COMPONENTS

2cVM controls the ability of components to produce external output through WebAssembly's capability-based security model. A component can only access system resources that are explicitly declared in its WIT interface imports. In particular, writing output requires importing the appropriate WASI capabilities (e.g., filesystem access). As a result, any component that is technically capable of emitting data is identifiable from its interface definition and is explicitly referenced in the *Commitment Manifest*. This provides an auditable record of which components are granted the authority to write results during execution.

Access to those results by external parties is controlled separately. Connectors are not components within the execution environment but external actors whose access rights are defined in the *Commitment Manifest*. The manifest specifies which connectors are allowed to retrieve particular output files produced during the computation. Consequently, both the ability to generate outputs and the entities permitted to consume them are explicitly declared and reviewable during the commitment phase.

While this mechanism constrains which components can produce outputs and which connectors may access them, it does not reason about the semantic content of the produced results. A component that is legitimately granted an output capability could still encode sensitive information in its output. Such behavior does not violate the 2cVM security model, since the existence of the output channel and the parties allowed to receive it are explicitly declared, but it may still be undesirable in certain collaborative scenarios.

A potential extension is the introduction of *output-filter* WebAssembly components placed between producing components and the output directory exposed to connectors. Such filters could be supplied by data providers and perform rule-based validation, privacy sanitization, or statistical leakage checks before data becomes accessible to connectors. Because these filters would themselves be components referenced in the *Commitment Manifest* and attested as part of the execution chain, they could provide an additional verifiable control layer over the content of released outputs.

B. RA-TLS INTEGRATION

Another long-term goal is the integration of 2cVM with RA-TLS to allow remote parties to authenticate both the platform and its confidentiality commitments over standard HTTPS connections, with increased protection against man-in-the-middle attacks. This would require extending current server stacks to regenerate attestation-bound TLS certificates for each connection in order to prevent replay attacks. This regeneration is not supported in most web infrastructure today. Achieving this would unify attestation, policy enforcement, and secure data exchange in a single verifiable channel.

C. ALTERNATIVE INNER ISOLATION MECHANISMS

The current 2cVM design relies on the WebAssembly Component Model to isolate untrusted code within the confidential VM. This model enforces strict boundaries between components and limits resource access to explicitly declared imports, providing strong, analyzable isolation. However, the programming model can be restrictive, and compiling existing software stacks to WebAssembly components is not always straightforward. In addition, the evaluation in Section VII shows that the WebAssembly execution layer introduces measurable runtime overhead compared to native execution for certain workload classes, particularly those dominated by floating-point operations or irregular, memory-access-intensive patterns. Future work could therefore explore alternative inner isolation mechanisms that offer comparable security properties with simpler integration paths or different performance trade-offs. Potential candidates include user-space kernel interposition layers such as gVisor, which virtualize system interfaces to confine untrusted workloads. The objective is to preserve fine-grained isolation and explicit resource control while making it easier to adapt existing applications to the 2cVM architecture.

D. PRACTICAL DEPLOYMENT CONSIDERATIONS

Moving from the current proof-of-concept to a production-ready system requires addressing several concerns that are orthogonal to the core isolation architecture but essential for real-world adoption. On the regulatory side, deployments that process personal data must comply with frameworks such as the GDPR, including requirements around lawful basis, data minimization, and data subject rights; the Commitment Manifest's explicit enumeration of data flows and authorized outputs provides a foundation for demonstrating compliance, but integration with organizational data protection processes remains future work. Dispute resolution mechanisms, such as tamper-evident logging of manifest negotiation and execution outcomes, are needed to support auditability when participants disagree on results or adherence to agreed terms. Operational tooling for lifecycle management, monitoring, and diagnostics of 2cVM instances is not yet developed. Finally, a cost analysis comparing 2cVM deployments against alternative approaches would inform adoption decisions but depends on workload characteristics and cloud pricing models that are outside the scope of this work.

E. FORMAL ANALYSIS OF COMPLEX THREAT VECTORS

Future work should include a detailed formal analysis of the complete 2cVM threat model. Complex attacks such as timing attacks or other side-channel attacks should be thoroughly investigated and formally mitigated. Given multiple parties can provide untrusted code processing sensitive data, this introduces novel attack vectors making defending against timing attacks very difficult. The untrusted code could, for example, use processing delays to transmit data out of band. Formal analysis of the added attack vectors

and investigation into mitigations against timing attacks is important future work. Additionally, while attacks against the WebAssembly and Confidential Computing substrates are described in literature [15], [31], [37], the combination of both could introduce additional attack vectors and requires a separate, hybrid analysis.

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